

Autonomous Ski-Companion Rescue Drone for Backcountry Incapacitation Incidents: A Scientific Research Proposal

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1. Abstract

Backcountry and extreme off-piste skiing exposes participants to time-critical emergencies, particularly avalanche burial, traumatic injury, disorientation, and incapacity. While avalanche transceivers, airbags, and satellite messengers reduce risk, they may fail to trigger timely rescue when the victim is incapacitated, unconscious, or unable to initiate an SOS (distress signal). This proposal investigates a **Ski-Companion Rescue Drone**: a lightweight UAV (Unmanned Aerial Vehicle) that follows a skier in uncharted terrain, detects anomalous events (e.g., sudden impact, abrupt immobilization, loss of motion consistent with burial or incapacitation), and autonomously performs three actions: (i) localize the last known victim position; (ii) mark the site by deploying a high-visibility flag/marker and activating a beacon; and (iii) transmit an SOS (distress signal) via an integrated communication chain (direct cellular where available, or via a direct or paired satellite messenger carried by the skier).

The research focuses on (a) feasibility and failure modes in harsh winter environments, (b) reliable anomaly detection with low false-alarm rates, (c) localization accuracy and marker deployment precision, and (d) regulatory and economic viability. The work will benchmark against existing off-the-shelf solutions (avalanche transceivers, RECCO reflectors, satellite messengers) and drone follow-me capabilities. The expected outcome is an experimentally validated prototype concept with quantified performance, safety constraints, and a commercialization pathway (if justified).

Keywords: Unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV); avalanche rescue; search and rescue (SAR); autonomous following; anomaly detection; sensor fusion; emergency localization and marking; satellite SOS (distress signal) messaging.

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2. Background and problem statement

2.1 Incident scale and urgency

Avalanche burial is a major cause of mortality in off-piste recreation. European avalanche services report that on average **around 100 people die in avalanches per year in Europe**, highlighting persistent risk despite modern equipment and forecasting (European Avalanche Warning Services, n.d.). In the United States (U.S.), the Colorado Avalanche Information Center reports an **average of ~27 avalanche deaths per winter across the last 10 winters** and notes that non-fatal “caught or buried” incidents are substantially underreported, limiting reliable annual estimates of total burials (Colorado Avalanche Information Center, n.d.). In Switzerland, long-term avalanche fatality statistics published by the WSL Institute for Snow and Avalanche Research (SLF) show persistent avalanche mortality across decades and provide multi-decade averages (WSL Institute for Snow and Avalanche Research SLF, n.d.).

Figure 1

Cumulative Probability of Survival by Time Buried Under Avalanche in Minutes

Note. The graph illustrates the cumulative probability of survival by time buried under avalanche in minutes. From "Avalanche Survival Rates in Switzerland, 1981-2020," by S. Rauch et al., 2024, JAMA Network Open, 7(9), e2435253 (<https://doi.org/10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2024.35253>). Copyright 2024 by Rauch et al. Reprinted under CC-BY license.

Survival probability is strongly time-dependent. A large Swiss cohort analysis (1981–2020) reports, as shown in Figure 1, survival probability remains high during early burial (e.g., approximately **91% within the first 10 minutes** in their dataset) and then decreases sharply as burial duration increases (Rauch et al., 2024). This motivates fast localization, immediate

marking, and rapid emergency notification—especially when the victim cannot self-initiate rescue.

2.2 Why current solutions still leave a gap

Existing safety measures are effective but have limitations in certain scenarios:

- **Avalanche transceivers** require correct usage by all party members and effective companion rescue; they do not automatically notify emergency services. Standardized avalanche beacon systems operate at **457 kHz** (European Telecommunications Standards Institute, 2017).
- **Satellite messengers** can send SOS (distress signal) alerts with location to an emergency response service, but they typically require the user to **press and hold** an SOS control to initiate the rescue workflow (Garmin, 2024). If the user is incapacitated, SOS (distress signal) may not be triggered.
- **RECCO reflectors** are passive and intended to make a person searchable by professional rescuers using RECCO detectors; the manufacturer explicitly states the RECCO reflector **does not replace an avalanche transceiver** (RECCO, n.d.).
- **Consumer tracking drones** can film and follow, but are not designed as safety systems. Sensor performance, tracking continuity, and obstacle-avoidance effectiveness can degrade in conditions relevant to avalanche terrain (e.g., poor visibility, low-light, weak texture/contrast scenes, and snow-covered surfaces), depending on platform and environment (DJI, 2025).

Problem statement. There is a safety gap for incapacitated victims and for rapid site marking + rapid alerting when companion rescue is delayed, impossible, or disorganized. A **Ski-Companion Rescue Drone** could reduce time-to-localization and improve rescue coordination by providing an independent observer, immediate marker deployment, and automatic SOS (distress signal) initiation through a paired messenger channel.

3. Proposed system concept (baseline)

System. A quadcopter-type UAV (Unmanned Aerial Vehicle) follows a skier in backcountry terrain. If an incident is detected (e.g., avalanche burial, incapacitating crash), the UAV hovers at the estimated victim location, as shown in Figure 2, deploys a high-visibility marker (e.g., orange flag), transmits an SOS (distress signal), and optionally lands near the location when battery falls below a threshold.

Core functions:

1. **Following / tracking:** Follow-me behavior using onboard vision, inertial sensing, and GNSS (Global Navigation Satellite System) (e.g., GPS) when possible.
2. **Incident detection:** Detect anomalous signatures (e.g., sudden acceleration spike, abrupt loss of subject visibility, prolonged stillness, unusual posture/orientation patterns, or loss of telemetry from a paired wearable).
3. **Localization:** Record last reliable coordinates + estimate drift; maintain a persistent marker position even if the drone must loiter or land.
4. **Marking:** Deploy a visible flag/streamer and activate an audio beacon.
5. **Alerting:** Send SOS (distress signal) via a direct or paired satellite messenger (or cellular network) and provide last coordinates, timestamps, and short video clips (with pre-consent).

Figure 2

Concept visualization of the proposed Ski-Companion Rescue Drone system

Note. AI-generated concept visualization of the proposed system in an incapacitation scenario; illustrative only (not experimental evidence). Generated with ChatGPT (OpenAI) from an author-written prompt.

4. Critical evaluation of the proposed system (flaws and risks)

4.1 Detection reliability (largest technical risk)

- Avalanche burial is visually ambiguous. Snow plumes, occlusion, and terrain shadows can cause false “burial” detections.
- **Stillness ≠ emergency.** A skier may stop to rest, dig a pit, adjust gear, or shelter. Stillness alone will generate false positives unless combined with robust context and user-controlled “rest mode.”
- **Signal/track loss is common** in ridgelines, trees, spindrift, and harsh lighting. “Lost target” is not equivalent to “victim buried.”

Mitigation direction (research focus): Multi-sensor anomaly detection with probabilistic classification and explicit user states (active / rest / emergency override). The design objective is to reduce nuisance alarms while preserving sensitivity to true emergencies.

4.2 Environmental constraints

- Battery performance drops in cold temperatures; strong winds reduce hover endurance.
- Rotor wash and acoustic waves can disturb loose snow near a burial site, potentially complicating probing/digging or exposing rescuers to secondary hazards.
- GNSS (Global Navigation Satellite System) degradation (e.g., canyon walls, multipath) can degrade localization; vision systems can also degrade under low-light or low-texture conditions (DJI, 2025).

4.3 Safety and human factors

- A low-flying quadcopter near a moving skier creates collision risk.
- Drone noise and attention demands can degrade decision-making in avalanche terrain.
- The system must be framed as an aid—not a replacement—for standard avalanche gear and training.

4.4 Regulatory and operational feasibility

Regulatory constraints are likely to be decisive for real-world deployment:

- In the European Union (EU), UAS (Unmanned Aircraft System) rules commonly require VLOS (Visual Line of Sight) in the “open” category, and they also constrain or prohibit dropping material from the aircraft in many common operating contexts (European Commission, 2019).

- In Türkiye (Turkey), UAV operations and importation involve national SHGM (Directorate General of Civil Aviation) procedures. Importation may require a “technical conformity” application under the SHT-İHA framework (Sivil Havacılık Genel Müdürlüğü, n.d.-a). In addition, SHGM publishes updates to operational/technical requirements (including communications/frequency compliance language) that a commercial safety system must track and satisfy (Sivil Havacılık Genel Müdürlüğü, 2025).
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5. Comparison to off-the-shelf solutions (including DJI)

5.1 Off-the-shelf safety solutions

- **Avalanche transceiver + probe + shovel:** The gold standard for companion rescue; standardized beacons operate at 457 kHz (European Telecommunications Standards Institute, 2017). Weakness: depends on companion competence and does not auto-alert rescue services.
- **RECCO reflectors:** Passive, designed for professional rescue detection; manufacturer guidance positions RECCO as an additional tool and explicitly not a replacement for a transceiver (RECCO, n.d.).
- **Satellite messengers:** Provide SOS (distress signal) initiation and location sharing, but typically require user action to initiate (Garmin, 2024).

Where a drone can add value (edge cases):

1. **Victim cannot trigger SOS (distress signal):** Drone can trigger SOS (distress signal) automatically when anomaly confidence is high, via a paired SOS device interface, or a direct link, e.g., to a satellite. (Garmin, 2024).
2. **Relay concept:** Wearable telemetry can communicate with the drone; the drone can pass coordinates/status to the paired messenger channel when direct user interaction is impossible, e.g., when the snow burying the skier prevents direct communication.
3. **Rest-mode control:** User can disable “stillness alarm,” reducing false positives.
4. **Last-footage intelligence:** With pre-consent, short clips from the last seconds before the incident can inform rescuers about likely burial zone, injury mechanism, and hazards.

5.2 DJI-specific comparison

DJI consumer drones offer mature tracking features and robust flight control, making them useful as prototyping platforms. However, they are not certified avalanche safety systems, and their manuals emphasize environment-dependent limitations of vision/obstacle-sensing that are

directly relevant to snow terrain. For example, DJI notes that the vision system can perform poorly near monochrome surfaces (including “pure white”) and that APAS (Advanced Pilot Assistance Systems) may not function properly over snow-covered areas (DJI, 2025).

Implication: A DJI airframe may accelerate early prototyping, but the proposed system still requires substantial additional sensing, validated incident logic, communications integration, and safety/regulatory compliance work beyond “off-the-shelf follow-me.”

6. Research objectives, questions, and hypotheses

Objective O1: Develop a UAV (Unmanned Aerial Vehicle) following + incident detection architecture suitable for harsh winter terrain.

Objective O2: Quantify detection performance (sensitivity, specificity, false alarm rate) for relevant incidents.

Objective O3: Achieve site-marking localization error below a defined threshold (e.g., $\leq 5\text{--}10$ m under usable GNSS conditions; empirically measured).

Objective O4: Demonstrate a reliable SOS (distress signal) transmission chain that works when the user cannot self-initiate.

Objective O5: Evaluate feasibility, regulatory constraints, and economic viability versus alternatives.

Research questions:

- **RQ1:** What sensor fusion and event logic can detect incapacitation/burial with acceptably low false positives in realistic ski scenarios?
- **RQ2:** How accurate can “last known position + hover/land + marker deployment” be under wind, snow, and GNSS degradation?
- **RQ3:** Does drone-based auto-alerting reduce time-to-rescue actions compared to “wearable-only SOS (distress signal)” in incapacitation scenarios?
- **RQ4:** Under what operational and regulatory constraints can the system be deployed safely?

Hypotheses:

- **H1:** Multi-sensor anomaly detection (motion + loss-of-track + contextual cues) can detect true incidents with materially fewer false positives than stillness-only logic.
- **H2:** Marker deployment + persistent beaconing improves rescuer convergence time even when exact burial position is uncertain.

- **H3:** A paired satellite messenger workflow can deliver SOS (distress signal) information even when the victim cannot act.
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7. Methodology and system design (proposed research plan)

7.1 Prototype architecture

- **Airframe:** Small quadcopter UAV (Unmanned Aerial Vehicle) with cold-weather battery management.
- **Navigation:** GNSS (Global Navigation Satellite System) + IMU (Inertial Measurement Unit) + barometer; geofenced “safe following corridor.”
- **Tracking:** Vision-based subject tracking with re-identification; optional wearable broadcast redundancy (e.g., BLE (Bluetooth Low Energy) / UWB (Ultra-Wideband)), subject to legality and feasibility.
- **Incident detection:** Probabilistic model using features such as acceleration spikes, abrupt altitude changes, loss of subject track, stationary duration, and wearable telemetry.
- **Communications:** Drone-to-wearable link + drone-to-satellite-messenger link (triggering a paired SOS device workflow where feasible).
- **Marker deployment:** Lightweight sheet in a highly visible color; beacon module activated on detection; optional audible buzzer.
- **Data capture:** Short rolling buffer (e.g., last 30–60 seconds) with pre-consent.

7.2 Experimental validation

- **Phase 1 (Controlled tests):** Ski slope tests with staged stops, falls, occlusions; measure detection and false alarms.
- **Phase 2 (Backcountry-like tests):** Complex terrain with ridgelines, trees, variable lighting, wind; measure tracking continuity and localization drift.
- **Phase 3 (Mock “burial” drills):** Avalanche training fields with safety controls; test last-known-position estimation, marking accuracy, and responder convergence time.

Metrics:

- Detection: sensitivity, specificity, false alarm rate per hour, time-to-detection.
- Localization: marker error distribution, hover/land reliability.

- Alerting: SOS (distress signal) success rate, message completeness, latency.
- Endurance: minutes of reliable follow + loiter under cold/wind.
- Safety: minimum separation distance, collision-avoidance performance.

7.3 Ethics, privacy, and consent

- Recording must be opt-in with clear consent, retention limits, and encrypted storage.
- Emergency sharing should be limited to rescue-essential information (coordinates, timestamp, short clip, device ID).

8. Feasibility and economic assessment (final verdict)

Technical feasibility (overall): Moderate—if the system is reframed from “the drone detects burial visually” to “the drone provides robust last-known localization + marking + automatic SOS (distress signal) initiation + (optionally) transceiver-related support.” The hardest problem is reliable incident detection without nuisance alarms. Cold-weather endurance, occlusion, and wind remain major practical constraints.

Operational and regulatory feasibility: Challenging. Continuous autonomous following in mountainous terrain conflicts with common VLOS (Visual Line of Sight) expectations and safety frameworks; and Türkiye (Turkey) requires compliance with SHGM (Directorate General of Civil Aviation) importation and operational processes (European Commission, 2019; Sivil Havacılık Genel Müdürlüğü, n.d.-a, 2025).

Economic sense:

- **Mass consumer product:** Weak to uncertain. Avalanche fatalities are tragic but numerically limited; many users already invest in transceivers/airbags and may resist paying for a complex, regulated drone system.
- **Professional / institutional market (more plausible):** Moderate potential. Ski guides, heliski operators, expedition leaders, and ski patrol teams may justify higher cost for (i) rapid last-known location evidence, (ii) scene marking, and (iii) automated emergency messaging—especially for clients who may be unable to operate SOS (distress signal) devices. A rental/service model (per day/per group) is more realistic than individual ownership.

Bottom line: The concept is feasible as a research project and may produce a valuable rescue-assist tool. It is not yet credible as a standalone consumer “avalanche safety drone” without major work on detection reliability, strict safety constraints, and a compliant operational model.

The strongest near-term product framing is:

“A professional-operated UAV (Unmanned Aerial Vehicle) companion and evidence/marketing platform that accelerates rescue coordination when a skier becomes incapacitated.”

Nevertheless, the concept of specialized follow-me drones could have a wider scope than what is currently anticipated and a successful product design for the case of back-country skiing might have the potential of creating a domino effect of creating new markets.

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-Assisted Technologies: During the preparation of this work, the author used ChatGPT (OpenAI) for language editing and proofreading to improve readability. The author also used ChatGPT (OpenAI) to generate the concept visualization in Figure 2. The author reviewed and edited the content as needed and takes full responsibility for the content of the publication.

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